

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14903022

Self-Esteem, Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students In Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State

Dr. Richard O. Okere

**Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This study investigated self-esteem, locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. Six research questions and six null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 42328 students in public senior secondary schools in the areas. The sample of the study was 450 students drawn through stratified random sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire titled: Students Self-Esteem, Locus of Control and School Adjustment Scale (SSLSS) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by two experts in Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling at Ignatius University of Education. The instrument yielded a reliability co-efficient of 0.78 for (SSES), 0.85 for (SLCS) and 0.78 for (SAQ). Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was used in answering the research questions and testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Also, there was a moderate positive relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. Based on the results of the study it was recommended that students should be assisted to build up self-esteem as they study effectively in school, irrespective of their sex and age, teachers should help students realize the fact that success and failure is in their hands, and not associated with any external force and school counsellors should assist students in building their internal locus of control, self-confidence and self-esteem, which will in turn build their self-image and academic improvement.

Keywords: Self-Esteem, Locus of Control, School Adjustment

INTRODUCTION

It is believed that for a nation to experience quality education, that is, a process where the imparting and acquiring of knowledge through teaching and learning would meet-up with prescribed standard, the quality of her students cannot be overlooked (Olofintoye, 2011). The attempt to have quality in secondary education implies that the students must also possess desirable attributes and values. Students in secondary schools are adolescents. By this, they are expected to be confronted with some biological and psycho-social concerns. In order to be considered high-quality an education system should be effective in both impacting academic knowledge and fostering students' acquisition of social and personal skills that contribute to optimum school functioning and enable them to successfully cope with future developmental tasks. This expanded role, coupled with the recent focus on the need for schools to act as agent for promoting well-being, has resulted in a growing body of research into school adjustment and

associated variables (Slomp et al, 2017), with particular attention being paid to adolescent students' strengths.

These needs for personal fulfilment and social acceptance must be satisfied if a wholesome personality is to be attained. Enhancing quality education therefore does not end at providing cognitive impetus or meeting-up with academic or certification requirements, but includes an adjustment situation in which students would realize their strengths and weaknesses and how to cope with them. The nature of students' adjustment should be seen as a central or major determinant of the extent of quality that could be expected in an educational system.

Adjustment, in psychology, refers to the behavioural process by which humans and other animals maintain equilibrium among their various needs or between their needs and the obstacles of their environments. Human beings are able to adjust to the physical, social and psychological demands that arise from having inter dependability with other individual. Adjustment, as process describes and explains the ways and means of an individual's adaptation to his self and his environment without reference to the quality of such adjustment or its outcome in terms of success or failure. It is an organizational behaviour in life situations at home, at school, at work, in growing up and in ageing. It helps one to keep out basic impulses at tolerable levels, to believe in one's own abilities and to achieve desired goals. Thus, adjustment helps for self-initiated growth and development along intellectual, emotional, social, physical, and vocational dimensions. Adjustment refers to the psychological process through which people manage psychological process through which people manage or cope with the demands and challenges of everyday life. It connotes conformity; it deals with the way in individual adapts to his environment and demand of life. This includes how he relates to others (interpersonal) and how he deals with his responsibilities and inner feelings.

Psychologically, adjustment helps the individual to cope with demands and pressures of the outside world as well as the needs, desires and conflicts experienced from within.

School adjustment plays a fundamental role in an individual's life, and it is like a pillar on which the individual life is based. It is not only related to an individual's progress and achievement, but also their attitudes towards school, anxieties, loneliness, social support and academic motivation (Palak et al, 2017). School adjustment is the process of adapting to the role of being a student and to various aspects of the school environment (Palaket al, 2017). They maintained also that failure to adjust can lead to mental health issues and school refusal or school dropout and may require school counselling.

If a student is well adjusted to his environment, then he or she will be motivated to excel in the activities assigned during school, and it leads to academic achievement. Academic achievement is greatly based upon adjusting abilities of students. An individual is not born adjusted, it is his or her capabilities that make him or her adjusted in any environment.

Another variable of concern in this study is self-esteem which has also been linked to school adjustment. Makie (2019) defined self-esteem as the way we think about the self. The above definition sees self-esteem as positive or negative assessment or evaluation of oneself. Stephens (2020) described self-esteem as a person's over all self-evaluation or sense of self-worth. The definition means that the evaluation of ourselves gives us sense of self-worth.

Self-esteem is a product of learning. Parents or caregivers make the greatest contribution to our self-esteem. They are mirrors reflecting back to us an image of ourselves. Our experiences with others such as teachers, friends and family add to the image in the mirror. Relationships reinforce what we think and feel about ourselves. The image we see in the mirror may be a real a distorted view of who we really are. Based on this view, we develop either a positive or a negative self-esteem or self-image. The strengths and weaknesses we learn as children are internalized and affect how we act as adults today (Uhiara, 2018). Locus of control is another variable that is considered in this study. Locus of control refers to the extent to which people perceive outcomes as internally controllable by their own efforts and actions or as externally controlled by chances or outside forces (Myers 2005). It is a cognitive style or personality trait. It is mainly concerned with the attribution of learning outcome. According to Silverman and Casazza (2000), this phenomenon of attributing learning outcomes to either internal or external factors is referred

to a locus of control (Silverman & Casazza (2000). For instance, a student may attribute his poor academic achievement to the note being lengthy and difficult, instead of thinking of how to improve his reading skills.

Statement of the Problem

In the process of school learning activities and situations, students may encounter some psychological and social problems which may result in worries, anxieties and frustrations. The failure of students in secondary schools to adjust academically can lead to mental health issues and school refusal or school dropout. If students are not well adjusted to their school environment, then they will not be better motivated to excel in the activities assigned during school, and this could lead to poor academic achievement. Students who have developed inadequate personality feel insecure and are obsessed by feelings of inferiority. They tend to think of themselves as unwanted, unacceptable and incompetent. They lack the courage to meet the demands and expectations of school learning.

Over the years, students in secondary schools in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State have been facing some school adjustment problems which result in frustrations and anxieties. The researcher believes that poor school adjustment of secondary school students is due to poor self-esteem and external locus of control. A student with a poor self-esteem tends to be more anxious and less well-adjusted and less effective in the tasks at school. Students with external locus of control tend to blame their poor grades on things beyond their control, such as blaming teachers, poor textbooks or difficult tests which could lead to educational maladjustment. Hence, the core problem investigated in this study is to determine the relationship between the variables of school adjustment in terms of the personality trait of self-esteem and locus of control as they affect school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to investigate self-esteem, locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State. In specific terms, the following objectives were considered.

1. To identify the relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
2. To determine the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
3. To determine the relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender.
4. To examine the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions were stated to give direction to the study,

1. To what extent does self-esteem relate to school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?
- 2 What is the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?
3. To what extent does self-esteem relate to school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender?
4. What is the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were stated to guide the study testable at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

3. Self-esteem does not significantly relate with school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender.
4. Locus of control does not significantly relate with school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State based on gender.

Significance of the Study

There is a great need to know the relationship between self-esteem, locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students. Success in school performance improves the psychological well-being and mental health of students. Every student desires to perform well in academics. This study is of immense benefit to teachers, guidance counsellors, parents, government, school authorities and the general public.

This present study will help teachers to gain insights in improving school adjustment among students in the school system. It behooves on teachers to guide students to develop a positive sense of self or self-image and to help them have internal locus of control.

Also, guidance counsellors through this present study can help to provide educational or academic counselling as a strategy for developing a positive self of sense for academic progress. It will also help parents to give attention to the psychological well-being and mental health of their children in terms of enhancing the self-worth of their children.

Again, it will help the government to give attention to the psychological and emotional health of students as it affects school learning through the deployment of guidance counsellors to schools, not just in the urban areas but rural areas as well.

More so, it will help school authorities to improve school adjustment through the enforcement of the provision of guidance services in schools.

Finally, it will help the general public to grasp an understanding of the personality variables that affect school adjustment and performance.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is a central construct in clinical, developmental, personality, and social psychology, and its role in psychological functioning has been studied for nearly a century. Anierobi et al., (2021) maintained that self-esteem literally implies how much value people put on their self-concept. They defined self-esteem as one's subjective evaluation of self-worth or a person's belief about whether he or she is smart and pretty. In the words of Nwamkwo(2010), self-esteem is concerned with describing who you are and describing your qualities as a person the way you perceive yourself. Richard (1998) cited in Nwankwo (2010) defined self-esteem as the extent to which we like and accept or approve of ourselves, how worthwhile a person we think we are. Colman (2003) explained self-esteem as one's attitude towards oneself or one's opinion or evaluation of oneself, whether negative (unfavourable or low) or positive (favourable or high). It is also called self-evaluation, it is concerned with evaluating or assessing the extent you have regard for yourself, or you consider yourself a person of worth. We achieve our self-esteem (self-regard) by judging our abilities and worth and by comparing ourselves with other people. Otherwise you cannot know if you are a brilliant student, a good teacher, a kind person, a wicked human being, unless you compare yourself in a specific ability with another person.

Need for Self-Esteem

Since we all want to see ourselves in a positive light, every person on earth has need for self-esteem. The question for us to answer is why do we have need for self-esteem. There are two main answers to this: the first, according to Leary and Baumeister (2020), is that people are inherently social animals and that their desire for self-esteem is driven by this more primitive need to connect with others and gain their approval. In this way, our sense of self-esteem serves as a social metre, a rough indicator of how we are doing in the eyes of others (Makie, 2019).

The second is Terry Management theory by Solomon and Pyszczynski (1997) cited in Makie, (2019) who stated that humans are biologically programmed for self-preservation. Yet humans are conscious of and terrified by the inevitability of our own death. We cope with deep rooted fear by constructing and accepting cultural world views about how, why and by whom the earth was created, etc. These world views provide meaningful purpose and a buffer against anxiety. The investigators thought their experiment, found that people react to scenes of death or the thought of their own death with defensiveness and anxiety (Makie, 2019).

Development of Self-Esteem

It is surprising how often and how natural, it is to judge oneself. A person's self-image is the mental picture, generally of a kind that is quite resistant to change, that depicts not only details that are potentially available to objective investigation by others (height, weight, hair colour, gender, LQ score, etc), but also items that have been learned by that person about himself or herself, either from personal experiences or by internalizing the judgments of others (Uhiara, 2018).

Self-esteem or self-image is how you perceive yourself. It is a number of self-impressions that have built up over time. Self-esteem is important because how we think about ourselves directly affects how we feel about ourselves and how we respond to life. Self-esteem can determine the quality of our relationships with others. How we think and feel about ourselves influences the way we react or respond to life stressors. A positive self-image affects our physical, mental, social, emotional and spiritual well-being.

How am I? We have an inner sense of our adequacy and value. With a positive self-esteem, we own our assets and potentials while being realistic about our liabilities and limitations. A negative self-esteem focuses on our faults and weaknesses, distorting failure and imperfections. Negative self-esteem may be the result of accumulated criticisms that the person collected as a child which have led to damaging their own view of themselves. Children in particular are vulnerable to accepting negative judgements from authority figures because they have yet to develop competency in evaluating such reports.

Negative self-esteem is not always caused by other people. The person may be often told he or she is beautiful/pretty/handsome but cannot personally see it. Poor judgements on himself or herself can be disastrous if not controlled properly. Negative self-evaluations can arise from a variety of factors. A prominent factor, however, is personality type. Perfectionists, high achievers and those with "type A" personalities seem to be prone to having negative self-esteem. This is because such people constantly set the standard for success high above a reasonable, attainable level. Thus, they are constantly disappointed in this "failure".

Locus of Control

The personality trait of locus of control was developed by an American Psychologist called Rotter (1966). Myers (2005) defined locus of control as the extent to which people perceive outcomes as internally controllable by their own efforts and actions or as externally controlled by chances or outside forces. Silverman and Casazza (2000) explained locus of control as the phenomenon of attributing learning outcomes to either internal or external factors. Rotter (1966) cited in Liebert and Spiegler (2018) defined locus of control as each person's view of the source of his or her outcomes. For instance, a student may attribute his poor academic achievement to the note being lengthy and difficult, instead of thinking of how to his reading skills.

People who have been characterized as internal locus of control personalities believe that the reinforcement they receive is under the control of their own behaviours and attributes.

Those with external locus of control think that other people, fate, or luck control the rewards they receive. In other words, they are convinced that they are powerless with respect to outside forces. Powerful others control and chance control and two components of external locus of control (Rosolack & Hampson, 1991). Onukwufor (2012) stated that students who see themselves as internally controlled are more likely to do well in school. Internal locus of control students believe they have a firm grip on their situation and behave accordingly. They perform at a higher level on laboratory tasks than do external locus of control students. In addition, internals are less susceptible to attempts to influence them, place a higher value on their skills and are more alert to environmental clues that they use to guide behaviour. They report lower

anxiety and higher self-esteem, and are responsible for their actions and enjoy greater mental and physical health.

In contrast, students who have external locus of control attribute their success and failures to external factors or variables such as chance, luck, fate or actions of powerful others such as teachers. They always blame teachers, poor text books or difficult tests for their poor grades and academic performance.

School Adjustment

Iwundu (2018) sees adjustment as a person's or the individual's ability to integrate properly in or respond positively to his social environment as it affects his inter-personal relationship with people. Denga (1990) defines adjustment as the harmony, congruence or a goodness -of-fit between an individual and standards against which he/she is adjudged. To Ibudeh (1990) adjustment is the individual's general adaptation to his environment, and the demands of life.

Adjustment is behavioural process by which a person maintains balance among various needs that one encounters at a given point of time. Each and every situation of life demands that the person concerned should be able to effectively perform in accordance with some guiding principles and should be able to strike a balance among various forces. Adjustment is the process wherein one binds variations in the behaviour to achieve harmony with oneself, others or the environment with an aim to maintain the state of equilibrium between the individual and the environment.

Adjustment or coping ability explains why resilient people rise above extra ordinary stressful environments while other individuals blessed with more benign life histories, collapse under the weight of relatively minor stresses. Usually, a stressful circumstance is rendered considerably less stressful when a person successfully adjusts or copes with it.

A healthy and well-adjusted person should possess some observable behavioural characteristics. These behavioural patterns are according to the social expectations of an individual. These patterns include; awareness of his strengths and limitations, respecting himself and others, an adequate level of aspirations, satisfaction of basic needs, absence of critical and fault finding attitude, flexibility in behaviour, the capacity to deal with adverse circumstances, a realistic perception of the world, a feeling of ease with his surroundings and a balanced philosophy of life.

School adjustment has to do with the students' ability to cope effectively with the internal and external demands and pressures which the school environment imposes on him. For instance, attending lessons, being attentive in subject lessons, during assignments and not cheating in examinations, making good grades and scoring high marks, not dropping out of school among others. School adjustment is the individual's ability to cope with the demands of school learning. A student who is academically well adjusted persists at a given problem or exercise, does not with his academic pursuit or affairs and is worried when he scores low marks or notices a general low performance in his academic work. When a child is well adjusted in school, he respects the authorities of the school, relates well with teachers and students and does not engage in any act capable of tarnishing his good image and reputation.

RESEARCH METHDOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted the correlational research design. The correlational research design was chosen to determine how self-esteem and locus of control relate with school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 4328 students of nineteen (19) public senior secondary schools in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. There are 2031 male students and 2297 female. Students in number totaling 4328 in all. Source: (Planning, Research and Statistics Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, Port Harcourt, Rivers State).

Sampling Technique

A stratified random sampling technique was used to select 220 male students and 230 female students from the different public senior secondary schools in Etche Local Government.

Sample of the Study

A sample of 450 students of the various public senior secondary schools in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State was used for the study. The samples size of the study was determined using Taro Yamen formula which will yield the value of 400. From the obtained number which was the minimum sample size, the researcher decided to increase the sample size to 450 to facilitate greater generalization of findings.

Instrument for Data Collection

The study employed a questionnaire method of data collection. Subsequently, a questionnaire titled: Students' Self-esteem, Locus of control and School Adjustment Scale (SSLSS) will be used. The Self-made research instrument consisted of four sections. These were section A: Demographic data of respondents, section B: Students' Self-esteem Scale, section C: Students' Locus of control Scale and Section D: School adjustment Questionnaire. Section B of Students' Self-Esteem Scale (SSES) consists of ten items which offer four possible answer choices on always strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) were adopted. Section C of students' locus of control scale (SLCS) consisted of ten items and adopts the options: strongly Agree (SA), Agree(A), Disagree(D) and Strongly Disagree(SD). Finally, Section D of School Adjustment Questionnaire (SAQ) consisted of ten items with the options: Strongly Agree(SD), Agree(A), Disagree(D) and Strongly Disagree(SD).

Validation of the Instrument

To ensure the face and content validity of the instrument, copy of the instrument was given to the researcher's as well as two experts in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Their suggestions, corrections and modifications were integrated into the final version of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined through test-retest method for measurement of stability of the instruments. Simple random sampling was used to draw a pilot sample of 40 respondents outside the sample who possessed specific characteristics to the study sample from Obio/Akpor Local Government Area and Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. Copies of the instrument were administered to the 40 respondents. After an interval of three (3) weeks, the same instruments were administered to the same sample. The initial and the re-test scores of the sample were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics. The reliability coefficients of the various sections B, C and D included 0.78, 0.85 and 0.78 respectively.

Administration of the Instrument

The researcher administered the research instrument, with the help of two research assistants; to the respondents who were given sometime to provide answers to the items before they were retrieved. Four hundred fifty (450) copies of questionnaire were administered, while 420 copies were retrieved for data analyses

Method of Data Analysis

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics was used to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: To what extent does self-esteem relate to school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between self- esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Table 1: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of Self-esteem and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students

		Self-este	School adjustment
Self-esteem	Pearson correlation	1	0.765**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.012
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.765*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	420	420

Table 1 of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.765 with its corresponding p-value of 0.012 < 0.05 (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Two: there is no significant relationship between Locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers Stat.

Table 2: pearson's product moment correlation of locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students

		Locus of control	School adjustment
Locus of control	Pearson correlation	1	0.517**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.025
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.517*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	420	420

Table 2 of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.517 with its corresponding p-value of 0.025 < 0.05 (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Research Question Three: *To what extent does self-esteem relate to school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Three: self-esteem does not have any significant related to adjustment of secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Table Three 3a: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of Male Students Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students

		Self –esteem	School adjustment
Locus of control	Pearson correlation	1	0.753**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.016
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.756*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	420	420

Table 3a: of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.753 with its corresponding p-value of $0.016 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

There is no significant relationship between male student's self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche LG.A of Rivers State.

Table 3b: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of Female Self-esteem and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students

		Self-esteem	School adjustment
Female students self-esteem	Pearson correlation	1	0.740**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.018
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.740**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	420	420

Table 3b of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.740 with its corresponding p-value of $0.018 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a strong positive relationship between female self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore shows that there is significant relationship between female self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Research Question Four: *What is the relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender?*

Hypothesis Four: Locus of control does not significantly relate with school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State based on gender.

Table 4a: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of Male Students Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students

		Locus of control	School adjustment
Locus of controls of male students	Pearson correlation	1	0.505**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.020
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.505**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.020
	N	420	420

Table 4a of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.505 with its corresponding p-value of 0.020 < 0.05 (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a moderate positive relationship between locus of control of male students and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between locus of control of male students and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Table 4b: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of Female Students Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students

		Locus of control	School adjustment
Locus of control of female students	Pearson correlation	1	0.410**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.023
	N	420	
School adjustment	Pearson correlation	0.410**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.023
	N	420	420

Table 4b of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation results reveal that r-value of 0.410 with its corresponding p-value of 0.023 < 0.05 (which is less than) the chosen level of significant was gotten. This shows a moderate positive relationship between locus of control of female students and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between locus of control of female students and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

It was found that there is a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State which was statistically significant.

1. It was found that there is a moderate positive correlation between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State which was statistically significant.
2. It is found that there was a strong positive correlation between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State based on gender which was statistically significant.

3. It was found that there is a moderate positive correlation between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche L.G.A of Rivers State based on gender which was statistically significant.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Self-Esteem and School Adjustment of Secondary Schools Students

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation result revealed that r-value of 0.765 with its corresponding p-value of $0.012 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significance was gotten. This shows a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen level of significance, the null hypothesis rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche LGA of Rivers State.

This result is in agreement with the studies of OnyeKuruandzuru (2017) who found significant relationship between social self-esteem, and school adjustment of secondary school students. It also found out that there was significant relationship between academic self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students.

Similarly, this is probably because self-esteem helps the students to make a positive assessment of themselves and this helps them to adjust anemically.

Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Student

Pearson Product Movement Correlation results revealed that r-value of 0.0517 with its corresponding p-value of $0.025 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significance was gotten. This shows a moderate positive relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chose level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore, shows that there is significant relationship between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school student in Etche LGA of Rivers State.

This finding is in agreement with the studies of Ochieng (2020) who found significant relationship between locus of control orientation and school adjustment of Orphaned and vulnerable pupils. Similarly, this is probably because students who believe that they can perform a task adjust successfully in schools.

Self-Esteem and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students based on Gender

Pearson product Moment Correlation results of 4.3a revealed self-esteem of male students and school adjustment as (r- 0.753, P 0.016 < 0.05) indicating strong positive relationship between self-esteem of male student and school adjustment. Since the p-value is less than the chosen level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore shows that there is significant relationship between male's student's self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students.

Again, Pearson Product Moment Correlation results of 4.3b revealed self-esteem of female students and school adjustment as (r 0.740, p 0.018 < 0.05) indicating a strong positive relationship between female self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore shows that time is significant relationship between female self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche LGA of Rivers State.

This result is in agreement with Aishad et al., (2015) who found a significant difference between male and female students on self-esteem and academic performance scores, which indicate that female students have high scores on academic performance as compared to male students and males students level high scores self-esteem as compared to female students.

Locus of Control and School Adjustment of Secondary School Students Based on Gender

Pearson Product Moment Correlation results of table 4.4a revealed locus of control of male students and school adjustment as (r 0.505, p 0.02 < 0.05), indicating a moderate positive relationship between locus of control of male student and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than the chosen level of significance, the null hypothesis rejected. It therefore indicates that there is significant relationship between locus of control of male student and school students in Etche LGAs of Rivers State.

Also, Pearson Product Movement Correlation results of table 4.4b revealed locus of control of female students and school adjustment as ($r = 0.410, p = 0.023 < 0.05$), indicating that there is a moderate positive relationship between locus of control of female students and school adjustment of secondary school students. Since the p-value is less than hypothesis is rejected. It therefore indicate between locus of control of female students and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche LGAs of Rivers State.

This result is in agreement with the findings Amenek et al, (2015) who found that there is no significant difference between Personal adjustment and gender. This result further revealed that there was an interaction between gender locus of control with Personal adjustment.

Summary

The major followings of the study were:

- 1 There is a strong positive relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State which was statistically significant.
- 2 There is a moderate positive correlation between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State which was statistically significant.
- 3 There is a strong positive correlation between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender which was statistically significant.
- 4 There is a moderate positive correlation between locus of control and school adjustment of secondary school students in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State based on gender which was statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the research, the following conclusions were made. Self-esteem has strong positive relationship with school adjustment of secondary school students. There is also strong positive correlation between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school students based on gender and age. While, locus of control has a moderate positive correlation with school adjustment of secondary school students based on gender and age in Etche Local Government Areas of Rivers State, hence it was statistically significant.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the research.

- 1 Students should be assisted to build up self-esteem as they study effectively in school, irrespective of their sex and age
- 2 Self-esteem and locus of control are very important construct; hence teachers should help the students realize that success and failure is in their hands, and not associated with any external force.
- 3 Parents should also boost the self esteem of their children by providing their academic needs and other physical support for academic improvement.
- 4 Teachers should assist in improving school adjustment among students in the school system as they guide students to develop a positive sense of self-image.

REFERENCES

- Arshad, M., Zaide, S.M. &Mah Mood (2015). Self-esteem and academic performance among university students. *Journal of Education and practice*, 6 (1), 156-162.
- Bednar, R. L. & Peterson, S.R. (2020). *Self-esteem: Paradoxes and innovations in clerical therapy and practice* (11th ed). American Psychological Association.
- Brehm, S.S., Kassin, S. & Fein, S. (2015). *Social Psychology*. Houghton Mifflin.
- Coleman, A.M. (2003). *Dictionary of psychology*. University press.
- Denga, D.I. (2002). *Educational & social psychology for schools and other social organizations*. CATS Publishers.

- Flory, J.D, Raikkonen, K, Matthews, K.A. & Owens, J.F. (200) Self-focused attention and mood during every day social interactions. *Personality and social psychology bulletin*, 26, 875-883.
- Freed, R. & Thompson, M. (2011). Predictors of parental locus of control in mothers of pre-and early adolescent. *Journal of clerical and Adolescent psychology*, 40(1), 100-110.
- Halonen, J.S. & Santrick, J.W. (2021) *Human adjustment*. McGraw-Hill.
- Harter, S. (1990).Self and identity development. In S.S. Feedman & G.R. Elliott (Eds). *At the threshold. The developing adolescent*. Harvard University Press.
- Jensen, L. Olsen, J. & Hughes, C. (1990) Association of country, sex, social class and life cycle to locus of control in Western European countries. *Psychological Reports*, 67, 199-205.
- Joseph, RA, Bosson, J.K. & Jacobs C.G. (2003). Self-esteem maintenance processes: when low self-esteem may be resistant to change. *Personality and social psychology bulletin*, 29, 920-933.
- Juang, XL & Cillessen, A.H (2005) Stability of continuous measures of sociometric status: a meta-analysis. *Developmental Review*, 25, 1-25.
- Kinance, J. B. (2018). Mental health and education in B. Inko-Trinah (Ed) *Healthand children's education, education associates*.
- Leary, M.R. & Baumesters R.F. (2020). Function of self-esteem: socio meter theory. *Advances in experimental psychology*.
- Liebert, M. R. & Spiegler, M.P. (2018). *Personality strategies and issues*. Cole publishing company.
- Makie, J. S. (2020). *Fundamentals of social psychology*. Pearson Inc.
- Nelson, S. T (2018). Self-esteem and school adjustment of university students in Kenya. *Journal African studies on education and development* 2(1), 90-98.
- Njoku, J. (2014). *Personality and its theories* (2 ed). ADYUDO Press.
- Nwankwo, Q.C. (2010). *Psychological basis of counselling and adolescence perspective*, reprinted, university of Port Harcourt press.
- Olofintoye, TT (2011). Undergraduate adjustment needs on campus. *Procedia-social and behavioural sciences* 30.
- Onukwufor. J.N. (2012). *Fundamentals of social psychology* .Sambros printing press
- Onyekuru, B.K. &Zuru, M. (2017). The influence of self-esteem on school adjustment of what concern is it to the counsellor .*Global journal of educational research*, 16(1), 20-26
- Owen, S. (2006). Occupational stress among correctional superiors. *Prison journal*, 86. 164-181
- Palak, K.L, Kusum, J. &Payal, K.C (207) School adjustment, motivation academic and achievement among students. *International journal of research in social science* 7(10): 333-348
- Patil, M., Saraswathi, G. & Pa Dakannaya, P (2009). Self-esteem and adjustment among children with reading and writing difficulties. *Stud Home CommSci*, 3 (2), 91- 95
- Robinson, N.S. (2021). Evaluating the nature of perceived support and its relation to perceived self-worth in a documents. *Journal of Research in Adolescence*. 5,253-280.
- Schultz, DP & Schultz, S. E. (2013) *Theories of personality*. (10 ed.). Wadsworth.
- Silverman, S.L & Casazza, M.E. (2000). *Learning and development making connections to enhance teaching*. Bass publishers.
- Stephens, T (2019). *Introduction to social psychology: Concept, issues and applications*. Magic Touch Publishers.
- Strauman, TJ., Lemieux, A.M. & Coc, C.L. (1993). Self-discrepancy and natural killer cell activity Immunological consequences of negative self-evaluation. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 64, 1042
- Towensend, M.C. (2006). *Psychiatric mental health nursing*. F.A. Davis Company.
- Uhiara, A.C., Nnamocha, O & Njoku, J.C (2018) *Fundamentals of psychology* Ikenga Publishers
- Uwaoma, N.C. (2000). *Introductory Psychology* Rescue Publishers.
- Walters, T. (2016). Relationship between locus of control and school adjustment across different ages. *Journal of social and personality psychology*. 2(5), 102-110.